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Editorial

As populations grow and policies for mandatory public education put greater demand on schools to educate children and adults, how will states manage to provide quality education for all? One can illustrate it with the case of Brazil. Enrollment in basic education has risen steadily over the past decade reaching near universality. Federal policy has now included elementary education as part of what is considered a basic, mandatory education to be provided by the State. According to legislation, teachers must now hold a university degree to teach and are encouraged to pursue degrees in their area of specialty. These and other factors have fueled an increasing demand for education at the graduate and post-graduate levels. On the other hand it is known that the demand for new teachers will not be met by current graduation rates. Universities would need to grow at unprecedented levels in order to quench the demand for new teachers around the country, and curricula increasingly demand new skills of existing teachers and new specialists (African history, Sign language, Spanish, Sociology and Philosophy, Music, among others).

These trends can be seen in many countries around the world, both rich and poor. The movement for Open Education and Open Educational Resources is an attempt to mitigate these concerns. Open Education is by no means a new phenomenon. One could go back many years, but need only turn to Ivan Illich and his proposal for formal communities of learning for some insight. Already in the 70's he envisioned a world where people would "network" in order to teach and learn any topic of interest. To facilitate this free and open education, Illich envisioned the central role of the shared, communal resources and the need for open systems rather than centralized content distribution.

This is an area of great interest for those involved with OER. The movement for Open Educational Resources has grown exponentially over the past.

According to the most recent UNESCO/COL guidelines, OER can be defined as:

"...teaching, learning, and research materials in any medium that reside in the public domain or have been released under an open license that permits their free use and, in some instances, re-purposing by others. The use of open file formats improves access and reuse potential of OERs which are developed and published digitally. Open educational resources can include full courses, course materials, modules, textbooks, research articles, videos, tests, software, and any other tools, materials, or techniques used to support access to knowledge. OER is not synonymous with online learning or eLearning. Rather, many OER – while shareable in a digital format – are also printable. Given the bandwidth and connectivity challenges common in some developing countries, a high percentage of resources will be shared as printable resources, rather than being designed solely for use in online learning."

OER promotes the potential of the exchange, sharing, adaptation, and modification of content licensed openly, using open formats. This has led to exciting new ways to think about how educational content is created and used. At the same time we have come to realize the opening content has reframed by sustained divides between those who traditionally create and those who just consume, and has not led to massive uptake in remixing and adaptation by those who can create. How can we prevent a neo-colonization and one-way flow of content based on the massive amount of content published by richer nations? How do we promote worldviews and exchange if we do not build systems and capacity so that minority groups effectively contribute?

Our future holds immensely valuable promises based on OER: an OER-based university, global communities of learning, and the free exchange of open

content. But for these and other promises to come to life, there is an urgent need to discuss how educational resources can effectively be exchanged between the peoples of the world. If we are to find this global voice we must again go back to these borders and frontiers which are obfuscated by discussions which focus on wealthy nations and within the confines of higher education: boundaries between rich and poor, peripheral and mainstream, connected and disconnected. This will lead us to a fruitful revisiting of OER from the perspective of culture: instructional design, systems for dissemination and collaboration, capacity building in resource-poor locations, methods for development, among others.

These proceedings are the result of a meeting entitled 1st International Symposium on Open Educational Resources: Issues for Globalization and Localization. It stems from a long-time working group on Technology and Education financed through bi-national FIPSE-CAPES grant programs. It was born out of a set of concerns:

“The number and quality of these resources continue to grow, but an important question remains. How can these resources be accessed, reused, revised, remixed, and redistributed effectively? The concerns are mostly based in two fields: first, a technical concern in the infrastructures necessary to produce and disseminate ever more flexible resources; second, cultural concern with the possibilities that are made available by technical “openness” but nonetheless exclude the non-target audience from making use of these quality resources.” (From the Symposium call)

Invited researchers met at Utah State University during the month of April, 2011 not only to present these works, but to benefit from a great variety of perspectives and lively debate. You will find here a collection of original peer-reviewed articles that are the result of these discussions. We hope they will

contribute answers to the questions highlighted above. Plans for a second symposium are underway and we hope a large number of researchers from around the world will join us in thinking about these issues.

Proceedings presentations, more information on the authors, and other information on the Symposium and upcoming activities are available at <http://www.educacaoaberta.org/rea/eventos/symposium>.

Tel Amiel

Núcleo de Informática Aplicada à Educação (NIED)
University of Campinas (Unicamp/Brazil)

Richard West

Center for the School of the Future
Utah State University (USU/United States of America)

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